

**Deliverable:
Database/sharing platform
solution established**

Workpackage 2

Responsible Partner: DTU

Contributing partners:

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRPFBZ-1-WP2.5		
Project Acronym	DiSCoVeR		
Author	Tine Hald		
Other contributors			
Due month of the report	36		
Actual submission month	49		
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 7-Jan-22		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):		

Database/sharing platform solution established

This deliverable was compiled in December 2021, but the data-sharing platform was available from June 2021.

Short description of platform

The project consortium agreed to use the platform ScienceData.dk for storing and sharing the sequence data. More information about the Danish e-Infrastructure Cooperation can be found here: <https://www.deic.dk/en>. The platform is based on the Owncloud environment and fully EU-GDPR compliant given its client-side end-to-end encryption, server-side encryption with HSM support, ransomware protection application, auditing/logging module, and authorization management. [sciencedata.dk](https://www.sciencedata.dk) platform to store and share sequence data.

All partners for which it was relevant to have access to the platform was provided with a link so they could create themselves as users of the platform either using an existing institutional account or creating a new 'external collaborator' account. A meeting to demonstrate the sciencedata platform was held on May 27, 2021, and a plan for uploading sequence data was made. To date most sequence data have been uploaded (~1.9 TB – see figure below), but due to delays in sample collection, a few are still pending.

Name	Size	Modified
AMR	19.8 GB	2 months ago
Campylobacter	765.4 GB	6 minutes ago
Data_description	4.3 MB	7 days ago
Salmonella	1.1 TB	8 minutes ago
VTEC_STEC	25.3 GB	18 days ago
5 folders	1.8 TB	

Isolate ID	Year	Institute	Country	Source Group	Source Subgroup	Sample Type	Source Comment	Age group	Import (on)	Salmonella species	Salmonella enterica subspecies	Serotype
S21_0321-210409_3888.fasta	2021	PIWet	Poland	Livestock	Broiler_chickens	Environment_(farm/slaughterhous	dust		No	enterica	enterica	Enteritidis
S21_0320-210409_3892.fasta	2021	PIWet	Poland	Livestock	Broiler_chickens	Environment_(farm/slaughterhous	boot swabs		No	enterica	enterica	Enteritidis
S21_0293-210409_3893.fasta	2021	PIWet	Poland	Livestock	Broiler_chickens	Environment_(farm/slaughterhous	boot swabs		No	enterica	enterica	Enteritidis
S20_1860-210326_3825.fasta	2020	PIWet	Poland	Livestock	Broiler_chickens	Environment_(farm/slaughterhous	boot swabs		No	enterica	enterica	Enteritidis
S20_1853-210326_3824.fasta	2020	PIWet	Poland	Livestock	Broiler_chickens	Environment_(farm/slaughterhous	boot swabs		No	enterica	enterica	Enteritidis
S20_1775-210326_3823.fasta	2020	PIWet	Poland	Wild_animals	Other_wild_birds	Other biological samples	Siberian goldfinch / liver			enterica	enterica	Enteritidis
S20_1133_210315_3758.fasta	2020	PIWet	Poland	Livestock	Broiler_chickens	Environment_(farm/slaughterhous	boot swabs			enterica	enterica	Enteritidis
S20_0707-210409_3887.fasta	2020	PIWet	Poland	Livestock	Broiler_chickens	Environment_(farm/slaughterhous	boot swabs		No	enterica	enterica	Enteritidis
S20_0598_210315_3751.fasta	2020	PIWet	Poland	Livestock	Broiler_chickens	Other	intestine			enterica	enterica	Enteritidis
S20_0468-210409_3889.fasta	2020	PIWet	Poland	Livestock	Broiler_chickens	Environment_(farm/slaughterhous	boot swabs		No	enterica	enterica	Enteritidis
S20_0464-210409_3890.fasta	2020	PIWet	Poland	Livestock	Broiler_chickens	Environment_(farm/slaughterhous	boot swabs		No	enterica	enterica	Enteritidis
S20_0463-210409_3891.fasta	2020	PIWet	Poland	Livestock	Broiler_chickens	Environment_(farm/slaughterhous	boot swabs		No	enterica	enterica	Enteritidis
S20_0164_210312_3722.fasta	2020	PIWet	Poland	Livestock	Laying_hens	Unknown			No	enterica	enterica	Enteritidis
S19_2537-200703_2889.fasta	2019	PIWet	Poland	Livestock	Broiler_chickens	Environment_(farm/slaughterhous	boot swabs		No	enterica	enterica	Enteritidis
S19_2374-200703_2888.fasta	2019	PIWet	Poland	Livestock	Broiler_chickens	Environment_(farm/slaughterhous	boot swabs		No	enterica	enterica	Enteritidis

Harmonisation of sequence quality

Partners are either uploading i) raw sequence data, which are then run through the FoodQC pipeline at DTU (Salmonella and Campylobacter), or ii) assembled sequences, which should then adhere to a set of agreed quality criteria.

For STEC sequences, the DiSCoVeR partner ISS developed a specific pipeline using the Galaxy platform and the Aries webserver (<https://aries.iss.it/>). A training session demonstrating this pipeline was held on September 23rd, 2021, and a user manual was made available for all partners.

Agreed quality criteria for sequences of Salmonella and Campylobacter

Proposed quality assessment of Salmonella sequencing results:

From FoodQC pipeline or the Qualimap (and possible others) the following parameters can be assessed:

- Number of contigs: <500 (but preferably < 200-300).
- N50: high as possible
- Total basepairs: app. 5,000,000
- Depth of coverage: $\geq 30x$ calculated as $\text{Bases (MB)} * 1,000,000 / \text{total bps}$
- Phred score: ≥ 20 . Calculated as part of the trimming process.
- E.g. use checkM (<5% contamination, >95% completeness).

Proposed quality assessment of Campylobacter sequencing results:

From FoodQC pipeline or the Qualimap (and possible others) the following parameters can be assessed:

- Number of contigs: <500 (but preferably < 200-300).
- N50: high as possible
- Total basepairs: 1,600,000 – 1,900,000
- Depth of coverage: $\geq 40x$ calculated as $\text{Bases (MB)} * 1,000,000 / \text{total bps}$
- Phred score: ≥ 20 . Calculated as part of the trimming process.
- E.g. use checkM (<5% contamination, >95% completeness).

Link to FoodQC pipeline:

<https://bitbucket.org/RolfKaas/foodqcpipeline/src/master/>

Contamination is not checked as part of the FoodQC pipeline, but at the next step as part of species identification. Not part of the QC pipeline.

Link to CGE tools at DTU:

<http://www.genomicepidemiology.org/services/>